

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND CARBON EMISSION PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF THE CEMENT INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH

Shaikh Masrick Hasan*

Received Date: 03-03-25 Accepted Date: 15-06-25

Abstract

Grounded in stakeholder and legitimacy theory, this study examines how corporate governance factors influence carbon emissions performance in Bangladesh's cement industry. The study utilizes data from 2014 to 2023, focusing on four corporate governance factors, board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and the presence of an environmental committee, as main variables alongside carbon emission performance. Firm-specific variables such as return on assets, leverage, and firm size are also included as control variables. Using panel data from six cement companies covering 2014–2023, the study applies the feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method to address heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence. Robustness checks are performed using panel-corrected standard errors (PCSE), pooled ordinary least squares (Pooled OLS), and iterative estimation within the FGLS model. Overall, the findings suggest that corporate governance mechanisms have a significant impact on the carbon emissions performance of the cement industry. Board size is positively associated with carbon emissions, suggesting that larger boards may increase operations that contribute to higher carbon emissions. Conversely, board gender diversity and the presence of an environmental committee are negatively associated with carbon emissions, highlighting the beneficial roles of female directors and the environmental committee in reducing carbon emissions. Board independence shows no significant effect. Among the control variables, return on assets and firm size have a positive influence on carbon emissions, while leverage exhibits an insignificant but negative relationship. This study offers strategic insights for stakeholders, corporate executives, and governments in environmentally sensitive sectors, such as the cement industry.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Carbon emissions, Cement industry, Bangladesh, Board diversity, Environmental committee, Stakeholder theory, Legitimacy theory

1. Introduction

Carbon emissions and their impact on environmental degradation have become significant issues in global discussions, emphasizing the importance of corporate

* Associate Professor, Department of Finance, Jagannath University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, E-mail: masrick@fin.jnu.ac.bd, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5321-119X>

governance in steering sustainable business practices and environmental responsibility. The uncontrolled release of greenhouse gases into the environment and the heavy reliance on carbon-based fossil fuels are among the most pressing challenges facing businesses and economies worldwide in the 21st century (Hoffmann & Busch, 2008; Elsayih, Datt, & Tang, 2021). An increasing number of empirical studies explore how excessive carbon emissions can deteriorate a firm's value (Luo & Tang, 2014). Bui, Mosses, and Houqe (2020) opined that the role of corporate governance is essential for properly managing carbon emissions, enhancing sustainability, and encouraging responsible corporate practices.

Corporate governance is a key instrument for promoting organizational sustainability (Haque & Ntim, 2018). According to Oyewo (2023), strengthening corporate governance instruments is a key strategy for reducing carbon emissions. Top business entities of a country, particularly those operating in carbon-intensive and environmentally sensitive industries, are significant contributors to overall carbon emissions. For sustainable development, the United Nations (UN) highlighted some agendas for organizations to address environmental pollution, assigning responsibilities regarding climate change action to both public and private sector entities (Banerjee, Khan, & Husnain, 2021). The research problem was identified to investigate the association between corporate governance practices and carbon emissions in developing countries like Bangladesh. This research tries to evaluate how several elements of corporate governance, including board size, environmental committee, gender diversity, and board independence, impact the firm's performance, particularly relating to carbon emissions.

Despite the importance of corporate governance, controlling carbon emissions within this framework has received minimal attention in developing countries (Tsamenyi, Enninful-Adu & Onumah, 2007). Additionally, numerous studies primarily focus on developed countries, leaving a gap in the markets of developing nations where the significance of maintaining corporate governance factors is often overlooked. This study aims to identify this gap by investigating the effect of corporate governance on carbon emission disclosures within the cement industry in Bangladesh and contributing to a deeper understanding, offering potential implications for policymakers. To achieve this, the study formulates research questions focused on how board size, sustainability committees, gender diversity, and board independence impact carbon emissions disclosure. The proposed research questions are as follows: i) How do corporate governance characteristics correlate with the carbon emission performance levels in cement companies in Bangladesh? ii) How do corporate governance characteristics influence decisions in response to the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) among Bangladeshi cement companies?

The purpose of the research is to determine the effect of corporate governance determinants on carbon emission disclosure. An additional capital expenditure by firms leads to higher emissions of carbon in the environment. Stakeholders today want to know whether their investments are resulting in any environmental degradation. A firm's management can achieve a strategic benefit by increasing transparency and revealing more information about corporate governance and carbon

emissions. (Li, Liao & Albitar, 2020). Corporate governance can significantly impact carbon emissions disclosures, and companies that maintain proper corporate governance positively impact their carbon emissions performance.

The findings of this study offer valuable insights into how firms can improve their sustainability and environmental accountability. It highlights how corporate governance structures, such as board independence, board size, board gender diversity, and the presence of a board environmental committee, can influence carbon emissions and improve companies' ability to achieve better environmental performance while reaching global sustainability goals. Additionally, the results contribute to the existing body of literature on corporate governance and environmental responsibility of manufacturing companies, providing evidence specific to the cement industry in Bangladesh. Moreover, these insights may encourage policymakers to develop stronger regulatory frameworks that promote sustainable business practices, support carbon reduction strategies, and incentivize good governance in the private sector.

The remainder of the article consists of various sections. Section 2 highlights the literature review and the development of hypotheses. Section 3 describes the methods and methodology of the study, while Section 4 presents the main analyses, results, and discussions of the study. Finally, Section 5 consists of the conclusion of the paper.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Several studies in environmental accounting (Deegan, 2002; Neu, Warsame, & Pedwell, 1998; Taurigana & Chithambo, 2015; Matoussi, Chakroun, & Mbirki, 2017) have highlighted the relevance of stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory in explaining the influence of corporate governance on environmental performance and carbon emissions management. Legitimacy theory suggests that firms aim to align their actions with social norms and expectations to maintain their legitimacy among stakeholders (Burlea & Popa, 2013). This theory highlights the importance of organizations communicating environmental information to society. Stakeholder theory acknowledges that different interest groups have varying views toward a company's actions and capacities (Deegan, 2002). Despite their distinctions, stakeholder and legitimacy theories focus on the organization's interaction with its external environment (Neu et al., 1998).

In the context of environmental sustainability, firms are increasingly expected to address issues such as carbon emissions to align with global and local environmental norms. Legitimacy theory suggests that companies with robust corporate governance frameworks are more likely to adopt environmentally responsible practices, thereby maintaining legitimacy and avoiding reputational damage (Suchman, 1995). Therefore, a company with strong corporate governance is anticipated to demonstrate greater social responsibility, and directors are motivated to enhance their carbon performance by reducing their carbon emissions. Thus, this finding aligns with public

expectations, and reducing emissions helps justify the firm's ongoing operations (Luo, 2019).

According to stakeholder theory, firms should consider the interests of all stakeholders from customers up to employees, regulators and local community members whose choices and activities potentially affect them (Freeman & Phillips, 2002). This theory highlights the importance of corporate governance in managing relationships with stakeholders, ensuring that the company addresses their environmental concerns. Research revealed that company's governance structures help organizations to connect effectively with stakeholders about sustainability matters and carbon emission controls (Lee, Wang & Zhang, 2023). Stakeholders' demands and preferences are likely to explain the disclosure of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, reflecting a company's strategic focus on environmental and social responsibility (Matoussi et al., 2017). Through stakeholder theory, firms develop climate change policies along with implementing climate-related activities that focus on fulfilling stakeholder requirements and expectations (Liao, Luo, & Tang, 2015). A summary of the theoretical framework is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Summary of Theoretical Framework

Notes: Author's own work

2.2 Empirical Research

Previous studies (Khairunnisa, Astuti, & Hussein, 2024; Tanthanongsakkun, Treepongkaruna, & Jiraporn, 2023; Kılıç, & Kuzey, 2018) primarily explored the connection between corporate governance structures and an organization's social and environmental disclosures. The impact of corporate governance on the voluntary disclosure of carbon emissions has been investigated across various countries, including the USA, Europe, China, and Spain (Ben-Amar, Chang, & McIlkenny,

2017; Gonzalez-Gonzalez, & Zamora Ramirez, 2016; Liao et al., 2015). As carbon emissions become an increasing concern globally, a growing number of researchers and analysts study carbon reporting practices from different contexts around the world. Previous researchers also indicated that the amount of carbon emissions diminishes a firm's value, consequently affecting shareholder wealth.

However, managers tend to focus more on carbon reduction with a staggered board structure, which shields directors from market pressures. Nevertheless, poor management of the corporate board structure can lead to weaker carbon emission performance. This staggered board may enhance the corporate aspect by alleviating anxieties among managers, as there is the possibility of hiring managers for the board on a contract basis. They will be less inclined to spend incentives on short-term projects; rather, they will be more willing to adopt long-term perspectives that align their decisions with long-term value maximization and prioritize the reduction of carbon emission performance (Latif et al., 2020).

An empirical analysis conducted in Spain found that corporate governance factors impact the decision of an organization's carbon material disclosure and the level of transparency (Gonzalez-Gonzalez & Zamora Ramirez, 2016). A company's carbon emission disclosure and transparency levels are heavily influenced by social pressure, shareholder pressure, financial market demands, and international business connections. Another study reveals that GHG disclosures significantly impact industry type, company size, financial slack, and gearing, while having no effect on profitability, capital expenditure, and liquidity (Chithambo, 2014). A study examining climate change-related disclosures among S&P 500 index companies found that a company's financial resources influence its financial decisions regarding carbon emission disclosures (Luo, 2013). Stanny and Ely (2008) explored how company size, along with foreign sales and prior carbon emission disclosures, significantly influences the carbon emission performance of the companies.

Furthermore, a study examining the role of gender diversity in Canadian companies to address stakeholder demands on climate change issues identified that companies with greater gender diversity on their boards were more likely to disclose climate change-related information (Ben-Amar et al., 2017). Moreover, Hollindale, Kent, Routledge, and Chapple (2019) discovered that the quality and quantity of GHG disclosures show a direct positive relationship with the presence of female directors on executive boards.

Although prior research has extensively examined the link between corporate governance and carbon emission disclosures across various countries (Liao et al., 2015; Ben-Amar et al., 2017; Gonzalez-Gonzalez & Zamora Ramirez, 2016), there is a lack of empirical evidence from Bangladesh, particularly in high-emission sectors such as the cement industry. Existing studies primarily focus on voluntary disclosures and transparency, often overlooking actual carbon emission performance, especially in emerging economies. Moreover, research on the direct influence of governance features such as board size, independence, gender diversity, and environmental committees remains scarce within the Bangladeshi context. The cement industry, being a major contributor to national emissions, warrants focused investigation.

While previous work suggests that board structure affects carbon strategies (Latif et al., 2020), these dynamics are unexplored in Bangladesh's cement sector. This study addresses this gap by using firm-level data from 2014 - 2023 to analyze how corporate governance affects carbon emission performance, offering valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders.

2.3 Hypothesis Development

2.3.1 Board Size and Carbon Emissions Performance

Based on board size and corporate environmental performance (carbon emissions), corporate governance structures have gained considerable attention in recent years. A study by Liao et al. (2015) found that board size has a significant relationship with carbon emission disclosure. Walls, Berrone, and Phan (2012) found that board size has a positive impact on the environmental and social performance of a firm. Cheung and Lai (2022) explored that a larger board size of a firm was more likely to disclose transparency of carbon emissions reporting. Sari and Hudaya (2023) explored the effect of corporate governance, particularly board size and found that larger board sizes encourage greater accountability for carbon emission disclosures. Jizi, Salama, Dixon, and Stratling (2014) found that larger board sizes are correlated with voluntary environmental disclosure, including carbon emissions. The authors argue that board size has a positive impact on disclosure levels due to the broader mix of skills, experience, and stakeholder perspectives that can drive companies toward transparency and environmental accountability. Thus, based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis is made:

H₁: Board size has a statistically significant influence on carbon emission performance.

2.3.2 Board Independence and Carbon Emissions

A firm board of independent directors plays a vital role in ensuring board independence, performance, and efficiency that allows them to act without bias toward management, reducing the risk of managerial opportunism (Fama & Jensen, 1983). They are driven by internal and external factors such as perceived sustainable responsibilities that benefit the company in the long term and enhance their reputation (Zahra & Pearce, 1989). They promote truthful environmental reporting and accountability, driving organizations toward a carbon-free world, meeting stakeholders' needs, and supporting legitimacy (Mudiyanselage, 2018). The lack of stock ownership among independent directors enables unbiased decisions on carbon emissions, enhances environmental quality, and, consequently, improves corporate image (Mudiyanselage, 2018).

The number of independent directors on a company's board tends to correlate with lower carbon emissions, as these directors enhance accountability and oversight (Walls et al., 2012). This also suggests that independent directors are free from management influence, prioritizing long-term sustainability over short-term goals, and making policies to reduce carbon emissions in the environment (Birindelli, Iannuzzi, & Savioli, 2019). Consequently, firms with more independent directors

may adopt proactive carbon-reduction practices, ultimately contributing to lower emissions. Moreover, independent directors play a key role in corporate governance to address agency issues between shareholders and managers. They are responsible for enhancing climate initiatives and improving the quality of carbon emission reporting (Jizi et al., 2014). They also focus on long-term goals and are less influenced by short-term pressures, thereby enhancing sustainable reporting. The independence of directors from shareholders and management leads to a significant positive relationship with carbon emission disclosures (Hussain et al., 2016). Based on the above discussions, the following hypothesis is made:

H₂: Board independence has a statistically significant influence on carbon emission performance.

2.3.3 Board Gender Diversity and Carbon Emissions

The inclusion of gender diversity on boards is a key component of corporate governance, and researchers are examining its impact on corporate performance (Daniels et al., 2024). In a study, Birindelli et al. (2019) explain the significance of female directors on corporate boards. There are several reasons supporting a positive connection between female members of the board of directors and company disclosures. Firstly, women enhance decision-making capability by providing unique viewpoints, which helps improve risk analysis and opportunity evaluation. Secondly, having women on boards enhances corporate reputation by signaling to investors, employees, and customers that the company prioritizes women and minorities. Thirdly, research indicates that women tend to manage risk more effectively, leading to more cautious and balanced risk management practices on boards with gender diversity (Latif et al., 2020).

In a study, Konadu (2017) showed that female board directors tend to be highly committed, innovative, and diligent in board discussions. This correlation may result from the more rigorous oversight and comprehensive problem-solving abilities of diverse boards. Gender diversity on a company's boards enhances the firm's awareness of environmental issues (Liao et al., 2015). Evidence establishing a relationship between carbon emission disclosures and board gender diversity is scarce (Ben-Amar et al., 2017). Companies with diverse boards will outperform other businesses when implementing carbon reduction plans and sharing information with investors and stakeholders. Based on the above discussions, the hypothesis is made:

H₃: Board gender diversity has a significant influence on carbon emission performance.

2.3.4 Environmental Committee and Carbon Emissions

A firm's board that includes an environmental committee provides greater objectivity and strategic direction on sustainability, driving the effective implementation and evaluation of carbon-reduction initiatives (Liao et al., 2015). Such a committee supports the firm in engaging with stakeholders and aligning with their expectations, highlighting a committed approach to balancing environmental responsibilities

alongside business objectives (Michelon & Parbonetti, 2012). An environmental committee is responsible for sustainability, establishes goals, and ensures greenhouse gas reporting, which reflects the board's dedication to environmental accountability (Neu et al., 1998). Environmental committees contribute by strengthening management oversight of sustainability actions and providing strategic guidance on environmental matters (Rodrigue, Magnan, & Cho, 2013). Several researchers (Elsayih et al., 2021; Liao et al., 2015; Dixon-Fowler, Ellstrand & Johnson, 2017) demonstrated that organizations with environmental committees experienced superior carbon emissions performance. In contrast, Konadu (2017) explored the negative relationship between environmental committees and carbon emissions performance. Based on the above discussions, the hypothesis is made:

H₄: An environmental committee statistically significantly influences carbon emission performance.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Sample Selection and Data Source

This study utilizes 10-year observational data (2014–2023) from six out of seven listed cement companies in Bangladesh. One company was excluded to ensure a balanced panel dataset, as its inception occurred after the base year of 2014. Balanced panel data allows for consistent estimation and simplifies interpretation, reducing potential bias compared to unbalanced panels (Hsiao, 2007; Wooldridge, 2010; Hasan, Tawfiq, Hasan, & Islam, 2024b). The elements of corporate governance, including board size and independent directors, board diversity, and the environmental committee, along with carbon emissions data, are used in this study. The study also incorporates firm-specific variables, which include return on assets, leverage, and firm size. Data on corporate governance and firm-specific variables are collected from the audited annual financial statements of the companies, while carbon emissions data is obtained from 'Our World in Data'¹, following Friedlingstein et al. (2024).

3.2 Variables Description

The study analyzes the effects of corporate governance on carbon emission performance. Here, carbon emissions performance serves as the dependent variable, while corporate governance factors such as board size, independent directors, board diversity, and the environmental committee are considered independent variables. Following the studies of researchers Ben-Amar et al. (2017), Walls et al. (2012), Hasan, Tawfiq, Hasan, and Islam (2024a), and Kumalasari and Pratikto (2018), this study utilizes carbon emission performance alongside various corporate governance parameters (board size, independent directors, board diversity, and the environmental committee). Additionally, three firm-specific variables (return on assets, leverage, and firm size) are used as control variables. A brief discussion of the variables is provided in Table 1:

¹ <https://ourworldindata.org/co2/country/bangladesh>

Table 1: Description of Variables

Serial No	Variables Name	Definition of variables	Sources
Dependent Variable			
1	Carbon Emission Performance	<p>The annual carbon emission performance of a company is measured using the economic allocation method, which allocates industry-level emissions among firms based on their production output, economic value, or revenue contribution. This method reflects the societal causes of emissions resulting from the production process. The formula for calculating carbon emission performance is as follows:</p> $\text{Carbon Emission Performance} = \left(\frac{\text{Company's Output}}{\text{Total output of the Industry}} \right) \times \text{Total Carbon Emission of Industry}$	Deloitte (2024); Messagie et al. (2013)
Independent Variables (Corporate Governance Parameters)			
2	Board Size	This indicates the number of individuals on a company's board, including both executive and non-executive directors.	Liao et al. (2015); Walls et al. (2012)
3	Board Independence	<p>It indicates a board member who does not contribute to the regular activities of the company and has no material relationship with the organization. Board independence is the percentage of independent directors, which is measured using the following formula –</p> $\text{Board Independence} = \frac{\text{Number of Independent Directors in Board}}{\text{Total number of Board Members}}$	Mudiyanselage (2018); Hussain et al. (2016)
4	Board Gender Diversity	<p>Companies implementing women leaders on their boards of directors are known for their diversity of gender. The percentage of females on the board is used to measure the board's gender diversity, which is computed using the following formula -</p> $\text{Board Gender Diversity} = \frac{\text{Number of Women in Board}}{\text{Total number of Board Members}}$	Latif et al., (2020), Konadu (2017)

5	Board Environmental Committee	It helps a board of directors monitor environmental sustainability and reporting. A dummy variable is used to identify the presence of a board environmental committee, where 1 is assigned to the firm with an environmental committee; otherwise, it is 0.	Elsayih et al. (2021); Konadu (2017)
Control Variables (Firm-Specific Factors)			
6	Firm Size	It is a measurement of a business's operating capacity and scale. Here, the natural logarithmic value of total assets is used to measure the firm's size.	Liao et al. (2015); Hasan, Hossain, Islam, and Hasan (2023)
7	Return on Assets	It assesses the efficiency with which a company can utilize its assets to generate profits. The following formula is used to compute the return on assets- $Return\ on\ Assets = \frac{Net\ Income}{Total\ Assets}$	Kumalasari & Pratikto (2018); Hasan et al. (2024a)
8	Leverage	Leverage indicates the acquisition of borrowed capital to invest in assets, aiming for returns that exceed the costs of borrowing. Leverage is computed using the following formula- $Return\ on\ Assets = \frac{Net\ Income}{Total\ Assets}$	Liao et al. (2015); Hasan and Farha (2025)

3.3 Econometric Model of Data Analysis

This study employs the panel data analysis method due to unit and time differences following previous researchers (Sohag, Nabilah & Begum, 2015; Hasan et al., 2024a; Wooldridge, 2010). The following regression equation is applied for this study-

$$CEP_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BSIZE_{i,t} + \beta_2 BINDP_{i,t} + \beta_3 BGENDER_{i,t} + \beta_4 ECOM_{i,t} + \beta_5 Controls_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where *CEP* is the carbon emission performance used as a dependent variable. Besides, independent variables are *BFSIZE*, which indicates board size, *BINDP* which represents board independence, *BGENDER* denoting board gender diversity, and *ECOM* indicates the board environmental committee. Additionally, control variables refer to company-specific factors like firm size, return on assets and leverage whose effects are controlled in the regression analysis. Furthermore, β indicates coefficients, *i* indicates the time, *t* indicates the unit of the company and ε indicates the error term.

Relevant diagnostic tests are performed to verify the validity and reliability of the regression model. Firstly, the Shapiro-Wilk test results (Table 2) confirm that all study variables are normally distributed, as the p-values exceed the 0.05 significance threshold (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965; Hasan, 2024).

Table 2: Normality Test using the Shapiro-Wilk Test

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
Carbon Emission Performance	60	0.999	0.146	4.386	0.9999
Board Size	60	0.999	0.107	5.1	0.8901
Board Independence	60	0.998	0.208	3.572	0.1200
Board Gender Diversity	60	0.999	0.185	3.846	1.0000
Board Environment Committee	60	0.999	0.116	-4.913	0.9999
Return on Assets	60	0.998	0.213	3.519	0.8999
Leverage	60	0.998	0.235	3.304	1.0000
Log Firm Size (Core)	60	0.998	0.305	2.705	0.9970

*Statistically Significant ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1*

Notes: This table presents the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality conducted on key study variables from 2014 to 2023, using annual data from six cement companies in Bangladesh. The test examines whether each variable is normally distributed. Given that all p-values exceed the 0.05 significance level, none of the variables show statistically significant deviation from normality. Therefore, it can be concluded that all variables are normally distributed.

Secondly, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test (see Panel A of Table 3) indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity ($\text{Chi}^2 = 49.52$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the findings of Glejser (1969) and Li and Yao (2019). Thirdly, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation (see Panel B of Table 3) yields significant results ($F = 12.02$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting serial correlation in line with Wooldridge (2010) and Hasan, Islam, Tawfiq, and Saha (2025). Finally, the Pesaran test for cross-sectional dependence (see Panel C of Table 3) reveals significant dependence across entities ($\text{CD} = 2.23$, $p < 0.05$), supporting the conclusions of Born and Breitung (2016) and Richey (2010).

Table 3: Results of Heteroscedasticity, Autocorrelation, and Cross-Sectional Dependence Test

Dependent Variable	Panel A	Panel B	Panel C
	Heteroscedasticity Test	Autocorrelation Test	Cross-Sectional Dependence Test
Carbon Emission Performance	Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test, $\text{Chi}^2 = 49.52^{***}$	Wooldridge Test, $F\text{-stat} = 12.02^*$	Pesaran's CD test = 2.01*

*Statistically Significant *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$*

Notes: Appendix 2 presents the results of diagnostic tests addressing key econometric concerns for the dependent variable, Carbon Emission Performance. In Panel A, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test confirms the presence of heteroscedasticity ($\text{Chi}^2 = 49.52$, $p < 0.001$). Panel B identifies first-order autocorrelation through the Wooldridge test ($F = 12.02$, $p < 0.05$). Panel C reveals cross-sectional dependence based on Pesaran's CD test ($CD = 2.01$, $p < 0.05$).

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics for corporate governance factors, carbon emissions data, and firm-specific variables from six listed cement companies in Bangladesh between 2014 and 2023. The carbon emission performance has a mean value of 0.1355, with a standard deviation of 0.0719. This suggests that, on average, a cement company in Bangladesh produces 13.55% carbon emissions annually with moderate volatility, indicating that the carbon emission performance values of the firms are relatively consistent and cluster around the average return. Board size has an average value of 9.00 with a standard deviation of 1.6833, showing that firms consistently maintain a similar level of board size. Similarly, board independence has a mean value of 0.2472 with lower volatility of independent directors, suggesting that the firms maintain a consistent level of independent directors. However, board gender diversity has a mean value of 0.0892, indicating that firms have fewer women on their boards. Moreover, the average value of the environmental committee is 0.6333, demonstrating that firms are concerned about environmental issues and sustainability.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	
Carbon Emission Performance	60	0.1355	0.0719	0.1301	0.0277	0.3612
Board Size	60	9.0000	1.6833	8.8889	7.0000	13.0000
Board Independence	60	0.2472	0.0413	0.2500	0.1250	0.3750
Board Gender Diversity	60	0.0892	0.0766	0.1110	0.0000	0.2500
Board Environment Committee	60	0.6333	0.4860	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000
Return on Assets	60	0.0487	0.0436	0.0447	-0.0401	0.1676
Leverage	60	0.5899	0.1806	0.5856	0.2406	0.9179
Log Firm Size (Crore)	60	7.0786	0.5192	6.9995	5.9523	7.9641

Note: The table displays descriptive statistics for carbon emissions, corporate governance indicators (board size, board independence, gender diversity, and environmental committee), and firm-specific variables (return on assets, leverage, and firm size) for six Bangladeshi cement companies over the period 2014 to 2023. Here, all variables, except firm size, were transformed using the two-step data normalization method to enhance normality, following the approach of Templeton (2011) and Hasan et al. (2024). Furthermore, firm size is transformed using the natural logarithm to improve the normality.

Additionally, the average return on assets (ROA) is 4.87%, and the volatility of ROA is 4.36%. This indicates that the average return of the firms and the overall volatility are relatively close, revealing higher volatility in ROA, causing some firms to incur losses relative to their assets due to the negative minimum ROA. The leverage ratio is 0.5899, which indicates that firms have more than half of their debt relative to total assets, suggesting a moderately high reliance on borrowed funds. Lastly, the average logarithmic value of firm size is 7.0786 crore, with a standard deviation of 0.5192, indicating moderate variation in operational scale across firms.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

Table 5 presents the correlation matrix of dependent and independent variables. Board size, return on assets, and firm size exhibit a significant positive correlation with carbon emissions, suggesting that larger boards and firms with higher profitability tend to produce more emissions due to expanded operations (Liao et al., 2015; Bedi & Singh, 2024). In contrast, board gender diversity, the presence of an environmental committee, and leverage are negatively correlated with emissions, implying that these factors contribute to improved sustainability practices. The presence of women on boards and environmental committees indicates a stronger environmental commitment, while higher leverage may drive firms to adopt cost-effective, low-emission strategies. Board independence shows no significant correlation with carbon emissions. All independent variables have correlation coefficients below 0.70, indicating a low risk of multicollinearity (Hasan & Hasan, 2024). Additionally, the average VIF value is 2.22, confirming no multicollinearity issue, as it remains well below the threshold of 10 (Hasan et al., 2025; Schroeder et al., 1990; Hasan, 2024).

Table 5: Correlation Matrix

Variables	CEP	BFSIZE	BINDP	BGENDER	BECOM	ROA	LEV	FSIZE	VIF
CEP	1.0000								
BFSIZE	0.5271***	1.0000							3.44
BINDP	0.0644	-0.2928*	1.0000						1.76
BGENDER	-0.1798**	0.3861**	-0.2328*	1.0000					1.87
BECOM	-0.1469*	-0.0622	-0.1705	0.1752	1.0000				1.61
ROA	0.4106***	0.3190**	-0.0673	0.2228*	0.0672	1.0000			1.58
LEV	-0.5107*	-0.6550***	0.2907**	-0.1716	0.1814	-0.5429***	1.0000		2.64
FSIZE	0.5745***	0.4280**	0.2558*	-0.2205	0.1788	0.1157	-0.2491*	1.0000	2.61
Average VIF									2.22

Statistically Significant *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Notes: The table demonstrates the pairwise Correlation Matrix, which demonstrates panel data analysis of selected variables such as carbon emission performance, corporate governance parameters (board size, board independence, board diversity and board environmental committee) and financial data (return on assets, return on equity, leverage and firm size) from 2014 to 2023 using the annual data of 6 company's corporate governance in cement industry. Here, CEP is carbon emissions performance, BFSIZE, BINDP, BGENDER, and BECOM are board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and environmental committee, respectively. In addition, ROA, LEV, and FSIZE represent return on assets, leverage ratio and firm size, respectively.

4.3 Regression Analysis Using Panel Data

To address heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence issues, this study employs the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) estimation technique, which is particularly appropriate for handling such challenges in panel data, as recommended by Beck and Katz (1995), Hoechle (2007), and Hasan et al. (2025). The regression results indicate that corporate governance parameters have a significant relationship with the carbon emission performance of the Bangladeshi cement industry (Table 6). The results specify that the coefficient of board size has a significant and positive influence on carbon emissions performance ($\beta = 0.0164$, $P < 5\%$), which supports hypothesis H₁. This finding aligns with Liao et al. (2015), who argue that larger boards may reflect firms with expanded operations, which naturally result in increased emissions due to higher output levels. In the case of board independence, the coefficient of board independence has a statistically insignificant negative relationship with carbon emissions performance ($\beta = -0.0815$, $P > 5\%$), which is inconsistent with hypothesis H₂. This may indicate that independent directors lack influence over environmental issues, possibly due to limited authority or symbolic roles (Rao & Tilt, 2016; Adams & Ferreira, 2009).

Table 6: Regression Results on the Influence of Corporate Governance on Carbon Emission Performance Using Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) Model

Variables	Carbon Emission Performance (Z-Statistics)
Board Size	0.0164* (2.56)
Board Independence	-0.0815 (-0.44)
Board Gender Diversity	-0.318** (-2.77)
Board Environment Committee	-0.0182* (-2.20)
Return of Asset	0.5191** (2.91)
Leverage	-0.0285 (-0.51)
Firm Size	0.0426* (2.31)
Constant	0.3011** (2.90)

Chi-Square	152.69***
Observations	60

*Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$*

Notes: This table consists of the results of the Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS) regression where carbon emission performance is the dependent variable and four corporate governance parameters (board size, board independence, board diversity and board environmental committee) are used as independent variables. Additionally, three firm-specific variables (return on assets, leverage and log firm size) are used as controlled variables of the study. The annual data from 6 cement companies were collected from 2014 to 2023.

The results also show that the coefficient of board gender diversity has a statistically significant negative relationship with carbon emissions performance ($\beta = -0.318$, $P < 1\%$), which supports hypothesis H₃. This finding suggests that companies with greater female representation on boards tend to have lower carbon emissions. Female directors may bring more environmental sensitivity and ethical awareness to corporate decision-making, leading to improved environmental performance. Prior research also indicates that gender-diverse boards are more likely to engage in sustainable practices and environmental governance (Post, Rahman, & Rubow, 2011; Liao et al., 2015). Finally, regarding the board environmental committee, the results show that the coefficient of the environmental committee has a statistically significant negative impact on carbon emissions performance ($\beta = -0.0182$, $P < 5\%$), which supports the hypothesis H₄. Companies with an environmental committee are more likely to prioritize sustainability and adopt practices aimed at reducing environmental harm, including carbon emissions. These committees often oversee the development and implementation of environmental policies, driving better decision-making and compliance with environmental regulations. This negative relationship suggests that the establishment of such committees leads to improved carbon emissions performance, as they foster accountability and ensure that environmental issues are addressed at the highest level of corporate governance (Kim & Lee, 2018).

The controlled variables, return on assets (ROA) and firm size, show a significant positive relationship with carbon emissions performance. A higher ROA indicates better financial performance and operational efficiency, often resulting in increased production, which can lead to higher emissions (Liao et al., 2015). Similarly, larger firms, due to their greater scale of operations, tend to consume more energy and resources, thereby producing higher carbon emissions (Han, Li, & Zhang, 2021). These findings suggest that while larger and more profitable firms may operate efficiently, their expanded activities contribute to a greater environmental impact. This highlights the need for sustainable practices in larger and more profitable firms. Furthermore, the leverage ratio shows an insignificant negative relationship with carbon emissions performance. This indicates that highly leveraged firms are often under pressure from creditors to adhere to sustainability guidelines and environmentally friendly practices. As a result, these firms are more likely to implement measures that reduce their carbon emissions, influenced by the financial and reputational considerations imposed by their debt obligations.

From the above discussion, it is evident that corporate governance factors, such as board size and firm size, are positively associated with carbon emissions, indicating that larger firms tend to have higher emissions due to their increased operations and resource consumption. On the other hand, governance mechanisms like board gender diversity, board independence, and the presence of an environmental committee show a negative relationship with carbon emissions. From a Stakeholder Theory perspective, firms with diverse boards and dedicated environmental committees are more likely to focus on stakeholder interests, including regulatory compliance and customer expectations, which drives them to adopt sustainable practices and reduce their environmental impact. Legitimacy Theory further suggests that companies with stronger governance structures, including environmental committees, align their actions with social norms and expectations, thereby upholding their legitimacy and demonstrating environmental responsibility. These findings suggest that firms with more robust corporate governance mechanisms are more likely to implement climate change policies and reduce emissions to meet stakeholder and societal demands. Additionally, control variables like return on assets (ROA) and firm size play a significant role, with higher ROA and larger firms leading to higher emissions due to enhanced production capacities and resource usage.

4.4 Robustness Analysis

Table 7 presents the robustness analysis of the influence of corporate governance factors on carbon emission performance using another dynamic model, namely the Panel Corrected Standard Error (PCSE) method, alongside the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares method to validate the findings of the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) (shown in Table 6). The results indicate that the PCSE and Pooled Ordinary Least Squares methods produce findings largely consistent with the FGLS model, except for the board environmental committee variable, where the coefficient remains negative in all three models but is statistically significant only under the FGLS estimation. Additionally, board independence demonstrates a negative but statistically negligible impact on carbon emission performance in the FGLS model, while the PCSE and Pooled OLS models indicate an insignificant but positive correlation. These differences may stem from the underlying functional differences in the estimation techniques. FGLS addresses heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and serial correlation to produce more efficient estimates, whereas PCSE and Pooled OLS may be subject to model limitations and estimation bias due to incomplete correction of underlying data issues. Moreover, board independence is commonly linked to improved governance and enhanced environmental outcomes (Walls et al., 2012; Birindelli et al., 2019); its influence may be moderated by contextual and institutional dynamics. In emerging market contexts such as Bangladesh, independent directors often lack the technical expertise necessary to engage meaningfully with environmental issues, or their roles may be more symbolic than functional. This limited capacity to actively monitor and guide environmental strategy can result in diminished influence over carbon emission performance, particularly in environmentally intensive sectors like cement manufacturing.

Table 7: Regression Results on the Impact of Corporate Governance on Carbon Emission Performance Using Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) and Pooled Ordinary Least Squares Methods

Variables	PCSE	Pooled OLS
	Carbon Emission Performance (Z-Statistics)	Carbon Emission Performance (T-Statistics)
Board Size	0.0174* (2.23)	0.0154* (2.13)
Board Independence	0.0836 (0.40)	0.0732 (0.35)
Board Gender Diversity	-0.2880* (-2.07)	-0.2630* (-2.01)
Board Environmental Committee	-0.0182 (-1.23)	-0.0180 (-1.12)
Return of Asset	0.4900** (2.59)	0.4787* (2.38)
Leverage	-0.0267 (-0.48)	-0.0285 (-0.52)
Firm Size	0.0418* (2.11)	0.0435** (2.92)
Constant	0.2990** (2.76)	0.2872* (2.66)
Adj. R-Square	60.78	60.78
Chi-Square	262.00***	
F-Statistics		33.68***
Observations	60	60

Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Notes: This table consists of the results of the Panel Corrected Standard Error (PCSE) and Pooled OLS method to validate the results of the FGLS method (Table 6). Here, carbon emission performance is the dependent variable, and four corporate governance parameters (board size, board independence, board diversity, and board environmental committee) are used as independent variables. Additionally, the study uses three firm-specific variables (return on assets, leverage, and log firm size) as controlled variables. The annual data from 6 cement companies were collected from 2014 to 2023.

To address the minor inconsistencies observed between the FGLS (Table 6), PCSE, and Pooled OLS (Table 7) results, a bootstrapping technique is employed using iterative estimation within the FGLS framework to enhance the robustness of the findings. The bootstrapped results, presented in Table 8, closely align with those of the original FGLS model in Table 6, thereby confirming the reliability and consistency of the estimates.

Table 8: Regression Results on the Influence of Corporate Governance on Carbon Emission Performance Using Iterative Estimation within the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) Framework

Variables	Carbon Emission Performance (Z-Statistics)
Board Size	0.00185*** (7.15)
Board Independence	-0.0267 (-1.11)
Board Gender Diversity	-0.482*** (-35.10)
Board Environment Committee	- 0.0118*** (-14.86)
Return of Asset	0.0684*** (3.60)
Leverage	-0.0223*** (-4.02)
Firm Size	0.00780*** (5.96)
Constant	0.0654*** (6.59)
Chi-Square	1506.44***
Observations	60

*Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$*

Notes: This table presents the regression results obtained via bootstrapping through iterative estimation within the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) framework, with convergence achieved after 15,999 iterations. The dependent variable is Carbon Emission Performance, explained by corporate governance variables (board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and the presence of a board environmental committee) along with firm-specific control variables (return on assets, leverage, and firm size). The analysis is based

on annual data from six cement companies in Bangladesh for the period 2014–2023 (n = 60). Bootstrapping is employed to enhance the robustness of the estimates, and the model demonstrates a strong overall fit, as indicated by the statistically significant chi-square statistic. The annual data from 6 cement companies were collected from 2014 to 2023.

5. Conclusion

In the context of growing global concern over climate change and environmental sustainability, this study investigates the effect of corporate governance on carbon emissions performance in the Bangladeshi cement industry. Using panel data from six cement companies over the period 2014–2023, the analysis primarily employs the FGLS method to address issues of heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence. Robustness is ensured through PCSE and pooled OLS estimations. The findings reveal that corporate governance factors significantly influence carbon emissions performance. Specifically, board size exhibits a positive impact, suggesting that larger boards are associated with increased operational activity and, consequently, higher emissions. In contrast, board gender diversity and the presence of an environmental committee are negatively associated with emissions, implying that inclusive and sustainability-focused governance structures contribute to better environmental outcomes. However, board independence does not show a significant effect, possibly due to limited influence or symbolic involvement in environmental oversight. Among control variables, both return on assets and firm size significantly positively affect carbon emissions, indicating that more profitable and larger firms tend to have greater environmental footprints due to expanded production. Although leverage has an insignificant effect, its negative sign suggests that financial pressure may encourage more sustainable practices. These results underscore the importance of strengthening internal governance mechanisms to align with environmental objectives and stakeholder expectations.

This study provides important implications and contributions for both practice and literature. It highlights the critical role of corporate governance, particularly board size, gender diversity, and the presence of environmental committees, in influencing the carbon emission performance of the cement industry in Bangladesh. The study informs stakeholders, policymakers, and corporate managers about how internal governance mechanisms can drive environmental accountability and sustainability by offering empirical insights from a developing country context. It contributes to the limited literature on carbon emissions in emerging economies by offering valuable insights specific to Bangladesh's cement sector, an area that has received little scholarly attention. Additionally, the study brings attention to the underexplored role of gender-diverse boards in reducing emissions, thus enriching the global discourse on environmental governance and offering new perspectives for future research.

This study has some limitations that offer avenues for future research. It focuses on only six cement companies in Bangladesh, limiting the generalizability of results across industries or regions. The reliance on secondary data may overlook informal governance practices or internal environmental efforts. Moreover, variations in carbon emission disclosure standards may affect data consistency. Future studies could include larger and cross-sectoral samples or conduct cross-country

comparisons in South Asia. Researchers may also adopt qualitative or mixed-method approaches to explore corporate culture and stakeholder influences. Additionally, incorporating regulatory pressure, market incentives, and stakeholder engagement could provide a more comprehensive understanding of carbon emission performance in developing economies.

References

- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291-309.
- Banerjee, S., Khan, M. A., & Husnain, M. I. U. (2021). Searching appropriate system boundary for accounting India's emission inventory for the responsibility to reduce carbon emissions. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 295, 112907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112907>
- Beck, N., & Katz, J. N. (1995). "What to Do (and Not to Do) with Time-Series Cross-Section Data." *American Political Science Review*, 89(3), 634-647
- Bedi, A., & Singh, B. (2024). Exploring the impact of carbon emission disclosure on firm financial performance: moderating role of firm size. *Management Research Review*, 47(11), 1705-1721. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-01-2023-0015>
- Ben-Amar, W., Chang, M., & McIlkenny, P. (2017). Board gender diversity and corporate response to sustainability initiatives: Evidence from the carbon disclosure project. *Journal of business ethics*, 142(2), 369-383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2759-1>
- Birindelli, G., Iannuzzi, A. P., & Savioli, M. (2019). The impact of women leaders on environmental performance: Evidence on gender diversity in banks. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(6), 1485-1499. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1762>
- Born, B., & Breitung, J. (2016). Testing for serial correlation in fixed-effects panel data models. *Econometric Reviews*, 35(7), 1290- 1316. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07474938.2014.976524>
- Bui, B., Moses, O., & Houque, M. N. (2020). Carbon disclosure, emission intensity and cost of equity capital: multi-country evidence. *Accounting & Finance*, 60(1), 47-71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acfi.12492>
- Burlea, A. S., & Popa, I. (2013). Legitimacy theory. *Encyclopedia of corporate social responsibility*, 21, 1579-1584.
- Chakroun, R., Matoussi, H., & Mbirki, S. (2017). Determinants of CSR disclosure of Tunisian listed banks: A multi-support analysis. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 13(3), 552-584. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-04-2016-0055>
- Cheung, K. Y., & Lai, C. Y. (2022). Board directorships and carbon emissions: curvilinear relationships and moderating roles of other board characteristics. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(12), 550. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15120550>
- Chithambo, L. A. (2014). Company specific determinants of greenhouse gases disclosures. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 15(3), 323-338. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAAR-11-2013-0087>
- Daniels, D. P., Dannals, J. E., Lys, T. Z., & Neale, M. A. (2024). Do Investors Value Workforce Gender Diversity?. *Organization Science*, 36(1), 313-339. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2022.17098>
- Deegan, C. (2002). Introduction: The legitimising effect of social and environmental disclosures—a theoretical foundation. *Accounting, auditing & accountability journal*, 15(3), 282-311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513570210435852>
- Deloitte (2024). *Roadmap: Greenhouse Gas Protocol Reporting Considerations*. Deloitte Accounting Research Tool (DART), 1-246. Retrieved from <https://dart.deloitte.com/USDART/pdf/f5a7930b-507f-4ec8-9a4d-b5f702e54001>. Accessed on 17 December 2024

- Dixon-Fowler, H. R., Ellstrand, A. E., & Johnson, J. L. (2017). The role of board environmental committees in corporate environmental performance. *Journal of Business Ethics, 140*, 423-438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2664-7>
- Elsayih, J., Datt, R., & Tang, Q. (2021). Corporate governance and carbon emissions performance: empirical evidence from Australia. *Australasian Journal of Environmental Management, 28*(4), 433-459. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14486563.2021.1989066>
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *The Journal of Law and Economics, 26*(2), 301-325.
- Freeman, R. E., & Phillips, R. A. (2002). Stakeholder theory: A libertarian defense. *Business Ethics Quarterly, 12*(3), 331-349. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3858020>
- Friedlingstein, P., O'sullivan, M., Jones, M. W., Andrew, R. M., Hauck, J., Landschützer, P., ... & Zeng, J. (2024). Global carbon budget 2024. *Earth System Science Data Discussions, 2024*, 1-133. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-965-2025>
- Glejser, H. (1969). A new test for heteroskedasticity. *Journal of the American Statistical Association, 64*(325), 316-323. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1969.10500976>
- Glejser, H. (1969). A new test for heteroskedasticity. *Journal of the American Statistical Association, 64*(325), 316-323.
- Gonzalez-Gonzalez, J. M., & Zamora Ramirez, C. (2016). Voluntary carbon disclosure by Spanish companies: an empirical analysis. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 8*(1), 57-79. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-09-2014-0114>
- Han, Y., Li, Z., & Zhang, X. (2021). Profitability, leverage, and environmental responsibility: An empirical study. *Journal of Corporate Finance, 68*, 101898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101898>
- Haque, F., & Ntim, C. G. (2018). Environmental policy, sustainable development, governance mechanisms and environmental performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment, 27*(3), 415-435. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2007>
- Hasan, M. H., Tawfiq, T. T., Hasan, M. M., & Islam, K. A. (2024a). Corporate governance dynamics in financial institution performance: A panel data analysis. *Investment Management & Financial Innovations, 21*(3), 292. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.21\(3\).2024.24](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.21(3).2024.24)
- Hasan, M. H., Tawfiq, T. T., Hasan, M. M., & Islam, K. A. (2024b). Risk in the shadows: Macroeconomic shifts and their effects on Bangladeshi mutual funds. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations, 21*(4), 371-384. doi:10.21511/imfi.21(4).2024.30
- Hasan, S. M. (2024). Does Islamic Mutual Fund Bear Higher Risk than Conventional Mutual Funds? An Empirical Analysis from Bangladesh: Islamic Mutual Fund vs. Conventional Mutual Fund. *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Business Research, 24*(01), 43-62. <https://doi.org/10.53461/jujbr.v24i01.43>
- Hasan, S. M., & Hasan, M. M. (2024). Effect of Macroeconomic Factors on Mutual Funds Risk and Return: An Empirical Study from Bangladesh: Mutual Funds Risk and Return. *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Business Research, 24*(01), 101-120. <https://doi.org/10.53461/jujbr.v24i01.31>
- Hasan, S. M., Hossain, S. A., Islam, R., & Hasan, M. M. (2023). Corporate Governance And Firms' Performance: Evidence From Dhaka Stock Exchange. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking, 13*(1), 28-38. <https://doi.org/10.46281/ijfb.v13i1.1947>
- Hasan, S. M., Islam, K. A., Tawfiq, T. T., & Saha, P. (2025). Triple pillars of sustainable finance: The role of green finance, CSR, and digitalization on bank performance in Bangladesh. *Banks and Bank Systems, 20*(1), 38-50. doi:10.21511/bbs.20(1).2025.04
- Hasan, S.M. & Farha, S.A. (2025). From Debt to Donations: Impact of Capital Structure on Risk and Return in Microfinance Institutions. *International Journal of Finance (IJFIN), 38*(2), 24-45. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.org/records/15064434>

- Hoechle, D. (2007). Robust standard errors for panel regressions with cross-sectional dependence. *The stata journal*, 7(3), 281-312.
- Hoffmann, V. H., & Busch, T. (2008). Corporate carbon performance indicators: Carbon intensity, dependency, exposure, and risk. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 12(4), 505-520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2008.00066.x>
- Hollindale, J., Kent, P., Routledge, J., & Chapple, L. (2019). Women on boards and greenhouse gas emission disclosures. *Accounting & Finance*, 59(1), 277-308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acfi.12258>
- Hsiao, C. (2007). Panel data analysis—advantages and challenges. *TEST*, 16(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11749-007-0046-x>
- Hussain, I., Singh, N. B., Singh, A., Singh, H., & Singh, S. C. (2016). Green synthesis of nanoparticles and its potential application. *Biotechnology letters*, 38, 545-560. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10529-015-2026-7>
- Jizi, M. I., Salama, A., Dixon, R., & Stratling, R. (2014). Corporate governance and corporate social responsibility disclosure: Evidence from the US banking sector. *Journal of business ethics*, 125, 601-615. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1929-2>
- Khairunnisa, A., Astuti, C. D., & Hussein, M. A. (2024). The influence of board diversity and environmental committees on carbon emission disclosures in Southeast Asian corporations. *J. Green Econ. Low-Carbon Dev*, 3(1), 26-35. <https://doi.org/10.56578/jgelcd030103>
- Kılıç, M., & Kuzey, C. (2018). The effect of corporate governance on carbon emission disclosures: Evidence from Turkey. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 11(1), 35-53.
- Kim, S., & Lee, M. (2018). Corporate governance, environmental performance, and the role of board committees. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 149(4), 905-925.
- Konadu, R. (2017). Gender diversity impact on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and greenhouse gas emissions in the UK. *Economics and Business Review*, 3(1), 127-148. <https://doi.org/10.18559/ebr.2017.1.7>
- Kumalasari, D., & Pratikto, H. (2018). Good corporate governance affects on corporate value through return on equity and return on asset of manufacture company. *KnE Social Sciences*, 114-126. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i3.1878>
- Latif, R. A., Yahya, N. H., Mohd, K. N. T., Kamardin, H., & Ariff, A. H. M. (2020). The influence of board diversity on environmental disclosures and sustainability performance in Malaysia. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 10(5), 287-296. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeeep.9508>
- Lee, C. C., Wang, Y., & Zhang, X. (2023). Corporate governance and systemic risk: Evidence from Chinese-listed banks. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 87, 180-202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2023.04.023>
- Li, Z., & Yao, J. (2019). Testing for heteroscedasticity in high dimensional regressions. *Econometrics and Statistics*, 9, 122-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecos-ta.2018.01.001>
- Li, Z., Liao, G., & Albitar, K. (2020). Does corporate environmental responsibility engagement affect firm value? The mediating role of corporate innovation. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 1045-1055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2416>
- Liao, L., Luo, L., & Tang, Q. (2015). Gender diversity, board independence, environmental committee and greenhouse gas disclosure. *The British accounting review*, 47(4), 409-424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2014.01.002>

- Luo, L. (2019). The influence of institutional contexts on the relationship between voluntary carbon disclosure and carbon emission performance. *Accounting & Finance*, 59(2), 1235-1264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acfi.12267>
- Luo, L. T. (2013). Comparison of propensity for carbon disclosure between developing and developed countries: A resource constraint perspective. *Accounting Research Journal*, 26(1), 6-34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ARJ-04-2012-0024>
- Luo, L., & Tang, Q. (2014). Does voluntary carbon disclosure reflect underlying carbon performance? *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 10(3), 191-205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcae.2014.08.003>
- Message, M., Boureima, F., Mertens, J., Sanfelix, J., Macharis, C., & Van Mierlo, J. (2013). The influence of allocation on the carbon footprint of electricity production from waste gas, a case study for blast furnace gas. *Energies*, 6(3), 1217-1232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en6031217>
- Michelon, G., & Parbonetti, A. (2012). The effect of corporate governance on sustainability disclosure. *Journal of management & governance*, 16, 477-509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10997-010-9160-3>
- Mudiyanselage, N. C. S. R. (2018). Board involvement in corporate sustainability reporting: evidence from Sri Lanka. *Corporate Governance*, 18(6), 1042-1056. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-10-2017-0252>
- Neu, D., Warsame, H., & Pedwell, K. (1998). Managing public impressions: environmental disclosures in annual reports. *Accounting, organizations and society*, 23(3), 265-282. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682\(97\)00008-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682(97)00008-1)
- Oyewo, B. (2023). Corporate governance and carbon emissions performance: International evidence on curvilinear relationships. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 334, 117474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117474>
- Post, C., Rahman, N., & Rubow, E. (2011). Green governance: Board of directors' composition and environmental corporate social responsibility. *Business & Society*, 50(1), 189-223.
- Rao, K., & Tilt, C. A. (2016). Board diversity and CSR reporting: An Australian study. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 24(2), 182-210.
- Richey, S. (2010). The impact of corruption on social trust. *American Politics Research*, 38(4), 676-690. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532673X09341531>
- Rodrigue, M., Magnan, M., & Cho, C. H. (2013). Is environmental governance substantive or symbolic? An empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 114, 107-129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1331-5>
- Sari, N. P. P., & Hudaya, R. (2023). The Effect of Good Corporate Governance Characteristics on Carbon Emission Disclosure in Carbon Intensive Industry. *Asian Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship and Social Science*, 3(04), 1444-1473.
- Schroeder, M. A., Lander, J., & Silverman, S. L. (1990). Diagnosing and dealing with multicollinearity. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 12(2), 175-187. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019394599001200204>
- Shapiro, S. S., & Wilk, M. B. (1965). An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples). *Biometrika*, 52(3-4), 591-611.
- Shrestha, N. (2020). Detecting Multicollinearity in Regression Analysis. *American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 8(2), 39-42. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajams-8-2-1>
- Sohag, K., Nabilah, A. B., & Begum, R. A. (2015). Dynamic impact of financial development on economic growth: heterogeneous panel data analysis of island economies. *International Journal of Economic Policy in Emerging Economies*, 8(1), 77-95. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEPEE.2015.068249>

- Stanny, E., & Ely, K. (2008). Corporate environmental disclosures about the effects of climate change. *Corporate social responsibility and environmental management*, 15(6), 338-348. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.175>
- Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *Academy of management review*, 20(3), 571-610. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1995.9508080331>
- Tanthanongsakkun, S., Treepongkaruna, S., & Jiraporn, P. (2023). Carbon emissions, corporate governance, and staggered boards. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(1), 769-780. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3174>
- Tauringana, V., & Chithambo, L. (2015). The effect of DEFRA guidance on greenhouse gas disclosure. *The British Accounting Review*, 47(4), 425-444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2014.07.002>
- Tsamenyi, M., Enninful-Adu, E., & Onumah, J. (2007). Disclosure and corporate governance in developing countries: Evidence from Ghana. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 22(3), 319-334. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900710733170>
- Walls, J. L., Berrone, P., & Phan, P. H. (2011). Corporate governance and environmental performance: is there really a link? *Strategic Management Journal*, 33(8), 885-913. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.1952>
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2010). *Econometric analysis of cross section and panel data* (2nd ed.). MIT Press.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2010). Econometric analysis of panel data: Some recent developments. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 24(5), 783-812. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6419.2010.00661.x>
- Zahra, S. A., & Pearce, J. A. (1989). Boards of directors and corporate financial performance: A review and integrative model. *Journal of management*, 15(2), 291-334. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920638901500208>

Cite as: Hasar, S. M. (2025). Corporate governance and carbon emission performance: A study of the cement industry in Bangladesh. *Jagannath University Journal of Business Studies*, 13(1), 23-46, <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789628>